

ISic0548

I.Sicily inscription 0548

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Cathedral

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR138306

1. D (is) M (anibus) .
2. Tac (itio) Iulia
3. no evok (ato) evocato
4. quondam
5. Aur (elia) Lucil
6. la coniu
7. gi karissi
8. mo carissimo et Iuli
9. us Tacitia
10. nus filius
11. heredes
12. posuerunt
13. merenti.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491791

EDR 138306

EDCS 22000875

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7289 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 41

Tusa, V. 1995. I sarcofagi romani in Sicilia.

At no.50

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